

Revisiting Environmental Kuznets Curves Through the Energy Price Lens.

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Research Highlights

- (1) EKC literature usually dismiss the major influence of energy prices.
- (2) Relative energy prices invalidate the evidence in favor of the EKC hypothesis.
- (3) Results may explain some contradictory observations found in the EKC literature.
- (4) Nowadays reduction in energy prices may break decarbonization trends.
- (5) Direct action by policymakers is required to break the positive GDP-CO₂ link.

Abstract

The goal of this paper is to provide new insights to elucidate the inconclusive results from the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) empirical literature. For the first time in empirical literature, an econometric analysis includes the relative prices for several energy sources. The paper provides strong evidence on the relevance of energy prices to CO₂ emissions. Accordingly, one reason for the lack of agreement in the EKC literature may be the absence of energy prices in empirical exercises. The presence of relative energy price changes in the econometric specification confirms a monotonic and positive relationship between CO₂ and gross domestic product (GDP). Therefore, we may conclude that there is a decoupling process but without reaching any turning point on that relationship. The policy implications are straightforward. Direct climate action by policy makers is required to break the positive relationship between CO₂ and GDP. That conclusion has been reinforced by the reduction of energy prices since the middle of 2014. Otherwise, the trend in energy prices may reverse the relative decarbonisation processes accounted for in recent years in major developed countries.

1 **1. Introduction**

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4 An important strand of literature searches for relationships between CO₂ emissions and
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6 gross domestic product (GDP), population growth, or both variables simultaneously.
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8 The underlying idea behind most papers in the literature is the Environmental Kuznets
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10 Curve (EKC) hypothesis: a sort of inverted U-shaped curve that relates pollution to
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12 economic development. It suggests that per capita CO₂ emissions may rise as a response
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14 to per capita income growth in the early stages of economic development up to a turning
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16 point, after which emissions begin to decline.
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21 The EKC hypothesis seems to beg the question of whether income growth beyond a
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23 turning point might serve as a solution to environmental degradation, rather than
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25 representing the source of the problem (Kaika and Zervas, 2013a, includes a very
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27 interesting literature review on this issue). Thus, the search for a turning point is central
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29 in the EKC literature as highlighted, for instance, in Galeotti and Lanza (1999). Their
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31 survey includes some references in favour of the EKC hypothesis but the estimated
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33 turning points are beyond the sample income levels (e.g., Holtz-Eakin and Selden,
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35 1995; Cole et al., 1997). Strictly speaking, these papers only provide evidence of a
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37 decreasing marginal propensity to emit greenhouse gases. There are also papers that
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39 estimate turning points within sample income levels. Some recent examples are
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41 provided in the work of Ang (2007), Coondoo and Dinda (2008), Apergis and Payne
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43 (2009), Dutt (2009), and Pao and Tsai (2010).
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51 An important policy implication derives from those papers providing evidence in favour
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53 of the EKC for CO₂ with turning points within sample income levels; further increases
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55 of incomes beyond the turning points lead to unambiguous reductions in CO₂ emissions.
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Consequently, favourable evidence in the EKC literature might legitimize lax political responses to climate change (or delays in adopting environmental policies [e.g., Beckerman, 1992]), as long as it provides a medium- and long-term solutions. That kind of statement is explicit or implicit in some papers' messages. In some cases, authors seem to agree with this view; others just mention that it may be the conclusion behind any eventual support of the EKC hypothesis and/or within-sample turning points (for recent examples, see, for instance, Richmond and Kaufmann 2006b; Apergis and Payne, 2009; Pao and Tsai, 2010; and Niu et al., 2011). Dutt (2009) makes an important point with regard to the view that the EKC hypothesis can legitimize lax political responses: "Based on all the findings so far, this [increase in income automatically resulting in lower emissions] does not seem to be the case. [...] Policies, combined with better institutions and public awareness could have helped reduce emissions, and in this study these happen to be associated with high-income countries".

Many papers have questioned whether the empirical data accommodates the EKC hypothesis. The main insight from the empirical literature is highlighted by Kaika and Zervas (2013a) as follows: "the EKC literature is quite large, and results are at best mixed. No clear conclusion can be drawn". As Agras and Chapman (1999) point out, the EKC hypothesis arises from a set of relationships that need to be fully identified. One important relationship that might influence the EKC hypothesis is the interaction between pollution and energy prices. However, energy prices have been omitted from most of the empirical specifications.

The main objective of this particular research is to provide additional evidence of the important role of energy prices in the EKC debate. Our main hypothesis is that

1 substitution and income effects in response to energy price changes exert a major
2 influence on the relationship between GDP and CO₂ emissions.
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5 This paper contributes to the literature by including, for the first time in an empirical
6 EKC model, relative energy prices (for coal, oil products and natural gas). The focus of
7 this paper is on OECD countries because they are more likely than other countries to
8 display the turning point predicted by the EKC hypothesis. Our results emphasise the
9 need to account for relative energy prices in order to avoid biased conclusions. The
10 paper develops in the following manner: Section 2 reviews the literature on the EKC
11 hypothesis; Section 3 presents the econometric methodology; Section 4 introduces the
12 data employed in this study; Section 5 provides the econometric results and some
13 further discussion; finally, Section 6 summarises the paper's conclusions and its main
14 policy implications.
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33 **2. A survey of the literature**

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35 The literature on the EKC hypothesis began, to our knowledge, with the research
36 agenda developed by the World Bank as part of the World Development Report (see,
37 for instance, the series of working papers published in 1992: Lucas et al., 1992;
38 Radetzki, 1992; Shafik and Bandyopadhyay, 1992). As a result of this line of research,
39 Beckerman (1992) concludes that the “strong correlation between incomes and the
40 extent to which environmental protection measures are adopted demonstrates that, in the
41 longer run, the surest way to improve your environment is to become rich”.
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54 The main pillars of the theoretical explanations in the EKC hypothesis are the income
55 effect, the structural effect and the abatement effect (see, for instance, recent surveys in
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1 Kijima et al., 2010; Jaunky, 2011; and Kaika and Zervas, 2013a). We may summarise
2 the main insights from this hypothesis as follows. Usually, economic development
3 results from structural changes experienced by national economies, from primary to
4 industrial and, later on, service–knowledge-based economies. Those structural changes
5 generate a national pollution transition in such a way that countries develop a path of
6 increasing per capita CO₂ emissions during the first stages of economic development.
7 Later on, they transition towards using less energy, and lower natural resource
8 consumption rates and eventually reduce per capita CO₂ emissions. In addition,
9 economic development (summarized as a greater income per capita) generates an
10 income effect that increases the consumption of goods and services and, therefore, per
11 capita CO₂ emissions. Finally, the abatement effect takes place when economies achieve
12 the greatest economic development. At that point, they will be able to invest more
13 resources (both private and public) in environmental protection and efficient
14 technologies that eventually reduce per capita CO₂ emissions (thanks to increasing
15 awareness of environmental problems that will impact consuming and voting
16 behaviours). Thus, the main hypothesis in the empirical literature is that the
17 combination of these three effects may result in an inverted U-shaped curve explaining
18 the CO₂-to-GDP relationship.

19 Despite the growing number of analyses providing support for the EKC hypothesis,
20 some literature surveys have questioned the validity of this hypothesis because of
21 inconclusive results, as many papers failed to provide such positive support. According
22 to several authors, some analyses may suffer from technical weaknesses and bias due to
23 omitted variables (for expositions on these issues, see, for instance, the surveys in Stern,
24 1998 and 2004; Dinda, 2004; He, 2007; and Kaika and Zervas, 2013a and 2013b).

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Consequently, Borghesi and Vercelli (2003) and Stern (2004) conclude that the EKC hypothesis might not be generally acceptable for use in the case of carbon emissions, although it may be correct for those studies based on local emissions.

Following this line of research, some recent papers stress the need for more robust statistical inferences on the EKC hypothesis. According to some authors, such as Vollebergh et al. (2009) or Musolesi and Mazzanti (2014), the controversy around using EKC to predict CO₂ may be related to the identification dilemma that researchers faced. They conclude that the EKC evidence is explained to a large extent by country-specific, time-related factors. In particular, Musolesi and Mazzanti (2014) find that out of a panel of 20 OECD countries, “only three Scandinavian countries – Denmark, Finland and Sweden – present some threshold effect on the CO₂-development relation, whereas for all other countries this relation appears to be monotonic and positive”. Unsurprisingly, Finland and Sweden present a very particular electricity-generation mix (as most of these countries’ energy is generated by hydroelectric and nuclear power plants). Besides, these countries benefit from participation in the integrated Nordic power market (known as Nord Pool, which also includes Denmark and Norway), thus further expanding hydroelectric generation capacity. Unfortunately, that particular mix of generation options is not accessible to all countries because of the unavailability of natural resources and political restrictions.

Following the line of reasoning highlighted in the previous paragraph, energy prices may be regarded as useful variables for improving the identification of robustness by disentangling the effect of GDP on CO₂ emissions from unobserved time-related effects. Agras and Chapman (1999) make the first attempt at including energy prices as an explanatory variable to study EKC for CO₂ emissions; the same variable is used for

1 all countries in the sample (real gasoline prices in the United States). Richmond and
2 Kaufmann (2006a), however, use country-specific, end-user prices (the price of light
3 fuel oil for industry) to take into account the differences in tax burdens and any other
4 structural constraints that affect the final prices. They find evidence in favour of the
5 EKC-type relationship, but it vanishes when the energy price is included. Additionally,
6 the coefficients associated with GDP are not significantly different from zero when
7 energy prices are included. Finally, Burnett et al. (2013) include a set of energy prices
8 (in a way that is very similar to our approach for studying energy-related CO₂
9 emissions) at the state level in the United States.
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22 The empirical literature has also tested the impact of elements aside from energy
23 prices—see for instance the latest studies in the *Energy Policy* journal on this issue:
24 Saboori and Sulaiman (2013), Song et al. (2013), Kanjilal and Ghosh (2013), Ozcan
25 (2013), Farhani et al. (2014), Lau et al. (2014), Robalino-López et al. (2014), Al-Mulali
26 et al. (2015), Yin et al. (2015). These additional elements are beyond the scope of this
27 paper.
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37 As mentioned, the controversy surrounding the empirical evidence against and in favour
38 of the EKC hypothesis deserves further research. Accordingly, we contribute to the
39 empirical literature by including relative energy prices for the first time.
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49 **3. Methodology**

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53 In this section, we outline the econometric methodology that we use to validate the EKC
54 hypothesis for CO₂ emissions. As previously mentioned, there is not a consensus in the
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1 empirical literature on the relationship between economic growth and CO₂ emissions.
2 This absence of consensus may be related to the identification dilemma researchers
3 faced when looking for a proper reduced form of estimation for the inverted U-shaped
4 curves, as long as “it is crucial to proper inference to impose identifying assumptions
5 that separate the effect of the independent variable from the unobserved effects”
6 (Vollebergh et al., 2009). Panel-data analysis should improve identification problems by
7 allowing for controls to capture unobserved fixed effects at the country level.
8 Nevertheless, these authors sustain that some identification problems remain as long as
9 pollution and income are both time-related through different unobserved channels, such
10 as, for instance, tendencies in technological developments. The lack of proper
11 identifying assumptions may yield biased and non-robust estimates.
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27 The purpose in this paper is to use end-user energy prices (in relative terms) to
28 disentangle the effect of GDP on CO₂ emissions from unobserved time-related effects.
29 On the one hand, an increase in relative prices may produce substitution effects (e.g.,
30 among different energy sources, between energy and other final goods, and between
31 energy and other intermediate inputs or primary factors). On the other hand, it may
32 boost investments in energy efficiency (e.g., by households, by firms for their
33 production processes, and by firms for the energy efficiency incorporated into the final
34 goods that they produce). Additionally, an increase in energy prices may reduce energy
35 consumption and CO₂ emissions because of a reduction in real income.
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50 Following the same reasoning, Musolesi and Mazzanti (2014) acknowledge that, apart
51 from bias due to omitted time-related factors, EKC estimates may also suffer from
52 functional-form and heterogeneity biases. They conclude that, for a panel of 20
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1 developed countries, the EKC evidence is explained to a large extent by country-
 2 specific, time-related factors (the same kind of results found in Vollebergh et al., 2009).
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 4 On this ground, we base our analysis on Musolesi and Mazzanti (2014) and additionally
 5 account for energy prices and energy independence. Thus, we estimate a fixed-effect
 6 panel data model with homogeneous income effects, individual fixed effects, and
 7 individual time effects, as follows:
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$$13 \quad d_{it} = \beta_1 y_{it} + \beta_2 y_{it}^2 + \beta_3 P_{it} + \beta_4 X_{it} + g_i(t) + u_{it}$$

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 19 Where $i=1, \dots, N$ and $t=1, \dots, T$. We will assume that the fixed effect u_{it} follows a one-way
 20 error-component model:
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$$23 \quad u_{it} = \mu_i + \nu_{it}$$

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 28 where $\mu_i \sim \text{IID} (0, \sigma_\mu^2)$ and $\nu_{it} \sim \text{IID} (0, \sigma_\nu^2)$ are independent (both of each other and
 29 among themselves).
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 35 In this model, d_{it} is the per capita CO₂ discharged into the environment, y_{it} is the per
 36 capita GDP at purchasing power parity, P_{it} is the set of energy prices, X_{it} is the set of
 37 variables accounting for the national endowment of energy resources, and $g_i(t)$
 38 represents country-specific time trends (the next section and Appendix A provide a
 39 detailed explanation of the variables).
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 50 The individual or country fixed effects (μ_i) are those idiosyncratic elements that are
 51 invariable in our time-frame analysis. This may include not only permanent conditions
 52 (e.g., institutions, culture, and geographic or climatic conditions) but also population
 53 distribution (e.g., urban sprawl; see Bataille et al., 2007, for further discussion). These
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1 features may be better understood as somewhat inflexible national characteristics in our
2 analysis (26 years); therefore, it is improbable that they can be dramatically modified by
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4 policy pressures or shocks in the short term. We have tested for the convenience of
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6 fixed-effects estimation in our panel of countries using the Hausman test, and fixed
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8 effects appear to be preferable to random effects. Moreover, we have tested our data for
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10 cross-sectional independence and the presence of unit roots. More details on all these
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12 statistical tests may be found in Appendix B.
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17 We also attempt to control for country-specific characteristics which are time-variable
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19 by including energy-independence share: the share of total primary energy supply that is
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21 domestically produced (with both domestic and international destinations) for each
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23 source. Energy-independence shares allow us to account for structural energy
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25 constraints such as shortages and excesses of domestic endowments with regard to
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27 energy consumption. Consequently, these shares might, to some extent, capture the
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29 nation's level of energy independence and, therefore, its energy security.
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35 However, the usual approach in the empirical literature is to include energy shares (out
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37 of primary consumption) instead of energy-independence variables (see, for instance,
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39 Marrero, 2010). The inclusion of energy shares (e.g., the energy mix) may be subject to
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41 criticism from a methodological point of view. Certainly, that sort of fuel-mix
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43 regression model might maximise the goodness of fit to the data. However, such a result
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45 may be the consequence of an accounting identity, which might bias the specification.
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47 Usually, energy agencies and national statistical services estimate carbon emissions as a
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49 weighted sum of fuel consumption multiplied by fixed coefficients that reflect the
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51 carbon content of each type of energy. As a result, changes in energy shares may
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53 explain changes in CO₂; therefore, little explanatory room is left for GDP. Thus, the
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inclusion of those variables in the empirical exercise will jeopardise the explanation of GDP's impact on carbon emissions.

Our empirical model also includes country-specific time trends, $g_i(t)$, which capture unobservable time-related factors that may heterogeneously affect different countries. These individual time effects may include elements such as trends (individual transitional changes) in technology, economic structure, and so on. Finally, our empirical model includes some other time-related factors that may homogeneously affect all countries, such as global economic shocks and policy developments (e.g., international agreements on trade and the environment), which are accounted for by year dummies.

We perform different specifications to assess the robustness of our results. First, we estimate a basic EKC equation that includes the energy-independence shares and the price for refined oil products but not year dummies and time trend variables. This specification allows us to compare our results with one of the few studies that includes energy prices (Richmond and Kaufman, 2006a). Furthermore, it provides a reference point for comparison with alternative specifications once we include additional variables such as supplementary energy prices, year dummies (two-way error model) and country-specific time-trend variables. For the latter, we assume that the individual time trend effects are linear, but that might be a questionable postulate. To check the robustness of our results from the parametric specification, we further relax that assumption by using non-parametric, country-specific time effects, following suggestions from some recent papers (e.g., Musolesi and Mazzanti, 2014).

1 Summing up, the approach followed in this piece of research is aggregation with
2 country-based insights, including: (i) individual fixed effects to capture any
3 idiosyncratic elements that are invariable in our time frame analysis; (ii) individual time
4 trends to capture any unobservable time-related factors heterogeneously affecting
5 different countries; (iii) national end-user energy prices (in relative terms) to improve
6 identification robustness; and (iv) the share of total primary energy supply that is
7 domestic, thus capturing to some extent the nation's level of energy independence and,
8 therefore, its energy security.
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23 **4. Data**

24 The focus of this paper is on 15 OECD countries: Austria, Belgium, the Czech
25 Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Poland, the Slovak
26 Republic, Switzerland, Turkey, the United Kingdom and the United States. According
27 to the EKC hypothesis, these countries may be rich enough (per GDPpc) to be on the
28 right side of the inverted-U relationship (for a similar approach, see the in-depth survey
29 in Kaika and Zervas, 2013a and 2013b). The lack of data for other OECD countries
30 (mainly energy prices, which are a key element in this research) restrict our sample to
31 an almost¹ balanced panel of countries and to the period of 1979 to 2004 (similar
32 constraints are reported in Richmond and Kaufmann, 2006a & 2006b). These data are
33 available in the databases “Energy Statistics of OECD countries, 2007 edition” and the
34 “Energy Prices & Taxes 2nd Quarter 2007” published by the International Energy
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55 ¹ We lack the first three observations for the price of natural gas in Turkey. This is not a problem as long
56 as the effect of natural gas is not significant for our preferred specification.
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1 Agency and OECD (Appendix A provides further details about the variables). We have
2 excluded previous years to avoid the known structural changes that occurred in the
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4 1970s in response to important oil-market disruptions, such as the Organization of the
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6 Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) oil embargo in 1973 and the Iranian
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8 Revolution in 1979. Moreover, the lack of data for some of the energy prices (mainly
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10 carbon and gas) in the time before the 1980s restricts the sample considerably.
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12 Similarly, we have excluded recent years to avoid the effects of economic shocks
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14 related to the financial crisis. Both oil-price and financial shocks may introduce
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16 structural breaks in the time series, thus causing changes in means or in the other
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18 parameters of the process that produces the series. These represent additional statistical
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20 problems that must be correctly handled to disentangle the impact of GDP on CO₂
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22 emissions from the effects of other variables. We try to avoid these sorts of problems to
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24 provide more robust statistical results.
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32 As mentioned in the previous section, we contribute to the empirical literature by being
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34 the first researchers to include relative energy prices. These data may convey some
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36 unobserved time-related effects of CO₂, either homogeneously in all countries (e.g.,
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38 international energy-market developments) or idiosyncratically (e.g., fiscal and market
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40 regulations that eventually impact end-user energy prices). Very few papers have
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42 included energy prices to explain the EKC hypothesis (see, for instance, the last survey
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44 published by Kaika and Zervas, 2013a). This may be due to the lack of data available
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46 for some energy sources (e.g., coal), even in OECD countries. As a result, some authors
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48 use oil prices as a proxy for all energy prices. However, any researcher who uses this
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50 specification will be unable to take into account the substitution effects driven by
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52 relative price changes. Accordingly, the relative prices of coal and gas with respect to
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1 refined oil products have been included in our empirical model as additional
2 explanatory variables.
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5 We have excluded electricity prices from the empirical model for two main reasons.
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7 First, it is a tradition in developed countries that electricity prices have been highly
8 regulated, with minor inter-year variations. These prices thus have a low explanatory
9 value for any empirical purpose, which probably explains the non-significance of
10 electricity prices in Richmond and Kaufmann (2006b). Second, other energies, such as
11 coal, oil and natural gas, may act as fuels for the production of electricity, thus causing a
12 sort of double-accounting channel for those prices; this should be avoided.
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15 Accordingly, we manage to include both a 20-year decline in oil prices and the increase
16 in those prices during the 2000s. During that period, nominal oil prices completed a full
17 reversal, returning to a price of approximately US\$40 in 2004 after last being at that
18 level in 1980, and reaching a bottom of US\$12 in both 1986 and 1999 in the interim. In
19 real terms, our database includes an important decrease in oil prices for the whole
20 period. That variability in energy prices (as illustrated here in the case of oil) should
21 reduce identification problems, thus providing a more robust model. Furthermore, the
22 OECD countries included are at different stages, in terms of both their development
23 process and their per capita CO₂ levels; the study includes European Union countries,
24 former Soviet Federation republics, the United States and Turkey). Table 1 summarises
25 the main descriptive statistics. For the empirical exercise presented in the next section,
26 all data are presented in logarithmic form.
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5. Results and discussion

This section presents the results, and it will highlight the important role of energy prices to disentangle the effect of GDP on CO₂ emissions from unobserved time-related effects.

5.1 Results

We first estimate a basic EKC equation, including the share of total primary energy supply that is produced domestically and the price for refined oil products but not the time variable. This is close to the specification provided in Richmond and Kaufmann (2006a), which is shown in the first column of Table 2. Keep in mind that we use, first the weighted average of industry and household refined-oil products (instead of industrial light-fuel oil, as in Richmond and Kaufmann, 2006a), and, second, proxies for national energy independence (rather than the energy mix, as used in Richmond and Kaufmann, 2006a).

[insert Table 2 here]

The results from the first column in Table 2 reveal a positive and significant effect of GDPpc and a negative effect of refined oil prices on carbon emissions. Actually, our results for GDPpc and oil prices are very close to the estimates in Richmond and Kaufmann (2006a). Additionally, we find a non-significant coefficient for the coal independence share and significant coefficients for oil and natural gas independence shares (which have negative and positive signs, respectively). The fact that CO₂ emissions may not respond to changes in the independence share of coal suggests that the independence shares might be capturing unobservable, idiosyncratic features; therefore, we should not attempt to draw a conclusion from their coefficients. The

1 negative sign for the oil independence share reinforces that view. We should keep in
2 mind that the purpose of energy-independence variables is to discard biased results from
3 the relevant omitted variables. In other words, we are much less interested in the
4 coefficients that are linked to energy-independence variables than in the robustness of
5 the empirical evidence with regard to the EKC hypothesis and the role played by energy
6 prices.
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15 We could make some comments regarding the carbon-free energy-independence share.
16 This figure measures the share of total primary energy supply due to renewable and
17 nuclear energy. We could assume that countries usually display a narrow capacity to
18 import/export carbon-free energy (apart from biomass sources, which are marginal in
19 our panel of data). Therefore, our results suggest that an increase in carbon-free energy-
20 independence shares contributes to a reduction in national carbon emissions.
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30 As mentioned in different sections in this paper, it is important to account for the prices
31 of different energy sources. As a result, the second column in Table 2 includes several
32 energy prices (refined oil, coal and natural gas), all of which had significant
33 coefficients. Surprisingly, regarding the results from the previous paragraph, this
34 provides evidence in favour of the EKC hypothesis and the existence of a turning point
35 (the second column in Table 2 displays a highly significant coefficient for the square of
36 GDP). These results are in line with those provided in Burnet et al. (2013). This is also
37 the case when no energy price is included in the econometric specification (although
38 this result was omitted in the text due to a lack of interest). However, Table 2 offers a
39 counter-intuitive result which suggests that a rise in the price of oil products may
40 increase CO₂ emissions (as the coefficient signs for energy prices are the same as those
41 reported in Burnet et al., 2013), which contradicts the evidence from the first column.
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1 Perhaps the reason for this unexpected result is that a rise in oil prices will increase coal
2 consumption, and the latter is far more polluting.
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5 We wonder whether these changes in coefficients for oil prices and the square of GDP
6 (as shown in Table 2) reflect the model's inability to accurately account for price
7 elasticities and substitution effects among energy sources. That is indeed the main
8 motivation for including relative energy prices. The third column in Table 2
9 corroborates this intuition. In particular, an increase in the price of coal relative to that
10 of oil would decrease per capita CO₂ emissions. Our results provide an additional
11 finding; we are no longer able to provide evidence in favour of the EKC hypothesis
12 because the squared GDP term becomes non-significant once relative prices are
13 included in the model.
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27 To check the robustness of that evidence, we proceed to the last two columns in Table
28 2, which include year dummies and country trends. Interestingly, the main conclusions
29 obtained from the third column in Table 2 remain unchanged: (i) relative energy prices
30 are significant variables in explaining CO₂ emissions, (ii) they are responsible for the
31 model's inability to provide evidence in favour of the EKC hypothesis, (iii) there is
32 almost no significant change in the coefficients, and (iv) there is a positive relationship
33 between GDP and CO₂ emissions. The elasticity of CO₂ emissions relative to GDP is
34 smaller than 1 (approximately 0.5, to be more precise). Finally, we obtain a non-
35 significant coefficient for the price of natural gas relative to that of oil, as expected
36 according to their similar carbon contents.
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52 A detailed study of the residuals of the preferred model (Column 5 in Table 2) shows a
53 correct fit. When we compare the observed values with the values predicted by the
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model for each individual country, we conclude that our model achieves a very good fit for all individual behaviours (see Figure 1). Appendix B provides further information on the goodness of fit and the residual analysis of the model.

[insert Figure 1 here]

5.2 Robustness of the model

As mentioned in the Methodology section, following the suggestions from some recent papers, like Musolesi and Mazzanti (2014), we have also checked the robustness of our linear model by allowing for non-linear effects of time relative to the response variable. More precisely, we have compared the linear specification with a partially linear model (see, for example, Härdle et al., 2004, for a general reference regarding partially linear models). With that purpose, we have worked with the regression model given in Section 3, in which the function $g_i(t)$ is non-parametric. Block (a) of Table 3 shows the results for a simplified version of the model with no country-specific or year-specific effects and a common non-parametric trend—that is, $g_i(t)=g(t)$ for all i . In this case, there is a total agreement between the linear model and the partially linear model in terms of the magnitudes of the coefficients and their significance. However, when non-parametric, country-specific time trends are included in the partially linear model (Table 3, Block b), changes in the magnitude and significance of some coefficients appear relative to the linear model (5) in Table 2. It is important to notice that the inclusion of country-specific trends enormously complicates the estimation procedure for the partially linear model; we have observed that non-stable estimators are produced. In particular, the

1 coefficient associated with the GDP is too large to be credible, as it would imply an
2 explosive increase in emissions. In our opinion, the fact that only 26 observations are
3 available for each country results in poor non-parametric estimators. To summarize,
4 taking into account both that the simplified models show a general agreement between
5 the linear and the partially linear models and that the relative energy prices available
6 constrain the number of observations for each country, we believe that the linear
7 approach is more suitable for the data analysed in this research. Consequently, as long
8 as we exploit the unobserved information contained in energy prices and energy-
9 independence indicators, we can conclude that (in this particular case) the gain from
10 using complex non-parametric estimation techniques is limited and that such a method
11 is inadvisable.
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27 [insert Table 3 here]
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30 **5.3 Discussion**

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32 Now we may proceed with the main insights from this piece of research. We have
33 provided empirical evidence of a positive relationship between GDP and CO₂
34 emissions. This conclusion is robust to the inclusion of year dummies and country-
35 specific trends that control for unexpected shocks (which are common for all countries),
36 technological developments (e.g., differences in the time frame for the adoption of new
37 technologies), and national circumstances (e.g., nuclear power development, natural
38 resource availability, geography and climate) captured by fixed effects and energy-
39 independence variables. As expected, a greater share of total primary energy supply
40 devoted to carbon-free energy contributes to a reduction in national carbon emissions
41 and a rise in national energy independence (and therefore energy security) by reducing
42 the consumption and import (respectively) of fossil fuels.
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1 The elasticity of CO₂ emissions relative to GDP is around 0.5. Therefore, there is indeed
2 a decoupling process between these variables. Nevertheless, there is no evidence of an
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4 eventual turning point, and we only find a relative decoupling. Therefore, once a high-
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6 enough GDP level is reached, we should not expect a reversal in the relationship
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8 between GDP and CO₂ emissions. Thus, GDP generates an important (but marginally
9
10 decreasing) positive influence on the path of CO₂ emissions.
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15 As expected, the relative energy prices exert a significant influence on CO₂ emission
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17 volumes associated with GDP levels. We may illustrate this channel through relative
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19 energy prices' impact on the EKC (Figure 2). This figure shows a hypothetical
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21 representation of a positive and monotonic GDP-CO₂ relationship for a particular
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23 country, both before (blue line) and after (red line) a significant rise in energy prices.
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25 Therefore, the increase in energy price, ceteris paribus, will shift the EKC downwards
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27 by decreasing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions for any level of GDP. Let us
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29 assume that the price increase takes places simultaneously with a sustained rise in GDP.
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31 The conjunction of these two trends can be represented by the black line in Figure 2.
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33 Thus, an empirical assessment of the data generated by this graphical representation
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35 (black line) might provide evidence in favour of the EKC, despite the fact that each
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37 single-coloured line represents the true relationship between GDP and CO₂ emissions.
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45 **[insert Figure 2 here]**
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48 The graphical analysis provided by Figure 2 emphasises the results from our empirical
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50 exercise: any research which fails to include energy prices may be jeopardising the
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52 robustness of its empirical results in favour of the EKC hypothesis. This result may
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54 explain why “the EKC literature is quite large, and results are at best mixed” (Kaika and
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1 Zervas, 2013a). Accordingly, relative energy prices provide valuable information for
2 disentangling the effect of GDP on CO₂ emissions from unobserved time-related
3 effects, thus reducing identification problems.
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7 From a political point of view, our results highlight that direct climate change policy is
8 required to break the positive relationship between CO₂ and GDP (e.g., technological
9 standards of energy efficiency and emissions, carbon pricing and support for
10 renewables). The call for climate action is further stressed by the current decline in
11 energy prices (particularly, the steep fall in oil prices since mid-2014). That trend may
12 reverse the decarbonisation processes of recent years in major developed countries.
13 Lower energy prices encourage greater consumption of fossil fuels and emissions, and
14 they dissuade investments in energy efficiency and renewable resources from both firms
15 and households, thus shifting the EKC upwards.
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30 Our evidence on the relevance of relative energy prices is linked to the adoption of
31 policies that eventually impact energy prices (e.g., green taxes, emission rights and
32 support policies for renewables), but there are of course many other policies available for
33 climate change action, as we have mentioned before. Some revenue-increasing policies
34 such as green tax reforms, based on the double-dividend hypothesis devised by Pearce
35 (1991), may produce additional benefits such as more efficient tax systems or lower
36 public deficits. Furthermore, environmental taxes might play an important role in easing
37 political constraints regarding the reform of public budgets in countries experiencing
38 fiscal stress (Gimenez and Rodriguez, 2016).
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53 Following this line of reasoning, the current drop in energy prices (e.g., oil prices' fall
54 from above US\$100/b in early 2014 to around \$40/b two years later) may represent a
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sort of low-price window for those policy makers who are willing to implement new political initiatives (erasing undesirable subsidies, increasing taxes for some products and sectors, etc.).

6. Conclusions and policy implications

This piece of research provides important evidence on the role of final energy prices in the EKC debate. In particular, the inclusion of changes in relative energy prices invalidates the evidence that we might otherwise find in favour of the EKC hypothesis in our econometric exercise. Our focus on final energy prices relates to the fact that they may provide valuable information related to unobserved, country-specific time factors. We may conclude then that the widespread omission of relative energy prices may explain the apparent contradiction of the results published in the empirical literature: significant empirical evidence both in favour of and against the EKC hypothesis. Thus, results from this paper emphasise the need to account for relative energy prices to avoid biased conclusions.

Accordingly, we can conclude that there is a positive (but marginally decreasing) relationship between GDP and CO₂ emissions (the elasticity of CO₂ emissions relative to GDP is around 0.5). We only find a relative decoupling between both variables. Consequently, we should expect more stress episodes on environmental grounds in the near future due to the instability in energy markets that has existed since 2014, pushing energy prices downward and national emissions upward for any level of GDP.

Direct climate action by policy makers is required to break the positive relationship between CO₂ and GDP. This could be implemented through several means, including

1 direct regulations (e.g., technological standards for energy efficiency and emissions)
2 and policy instruments based on the market (e.g., carbon pricing and support for
3 renewables). Actually, the latter kind of instrument may be preferred in a situation with
4 low energy prices as long as policy makers can take advantage of that scenario to
5 implement new climate-change initiatives (e.g., erasing undesirable subsidies or
6 increasing taxes for some products and sectors).
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Appendix

Appendix A: Variable definitions

CO₂ discharge on the environment: CO₂ sectoral approach (mt of CO₂).

Gross domestic Product per capita: US\$2000 using PPPs per person (expressed in thousands).

Total primary energy consumption: it includes oil, coal, gas and renewable (ktoe per person).

Weighted average price of oil products: US\$2000 using PPPs/kl. It is calculated as a weighted average of industry and household prices (we use the final consumption as weights). Industry prices include representative heavy fuel oil, light fuel oil and automotive diesel, but not fuels used for electricity generation. The household index includes representative gasoline and light fuel oil.

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Weighted average price of coal: US\$2000 using PPPs/ton). It is calculated as a weighted average of industry and household prices (we use the final consumption as weights). For coal, the industry index includes representative steam coal and coking coal. The household index includes steam coal.

Weighted average price of gas: US\$2000 using PPPs/m³. It is calculated as a weighted average of industry and household prices (we use the final consumption as weights).

Oil, coal, gas or carbon free energy independence: domestic production for each energy source before including imports and exports relative to total primary energy (ktoe).

Carbon free resources includes renewables and nuclear energy

Appendix B: econometric issues

Testing fixed-effects

Within this class of models, the fixed-effects specification is a common choice for macroeconomic analysis, and it is believed to be more appropriate than a random-effects model for two reasons. First, if the individual effect represents omitted variables, it is likely that the country-specific characteristics are correlated with the other regressors. Second, a typical macro panel is not likely to be a random sample from a larger universe of countries. Moreover, we have tested for fixed effects by using the Hausman test in all specifications; fixed effects are preferable to random effects.

Testing unit roots

1 The presence of unit roots may lead to specification bias. Accordingly, we test to
2 determine if the dependent variable contains unit roots as long as our panel-data
3 analysis relies on stationary data. To implement the right unit-root test for our panel, we
4 have to take into account its size—in this case, 15 unit panels (N) and 26 time periods
5 (T). For this type of panel (a small number of individuals and a small or moderate
6 number of time periods), it is typically assumed that N is fixed and that T tends to
7 infinity. A test in which N approaches infinity as the time dimension approaches infinity
8 could also be used, although such tests work best with large values of T and at least a
9 moderately sized N.
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11 Three tests might be applicable to our sample. The first is the LLC test (Levin, Lin and
12 Chu test: Levin, et al., 2002), which is recommended for panels of moderate size (i.e.,
13 between 10 and 250 panels and 25 to 250 time periods per panel). Additionally, the
14 requirement that N/T approaches 0 implies that N should be small relative to T (Baltagi,
15 2008). The second is the IPS test (Im, Pesaran and Shin test: Im et al., 2003), which is
16 appropriate when both N and T are fixed. Im et al. calculated exact critical values using
17 simulations. Finally, Choi's (2001) Fisher-type test, for which both the inverse-normal
18 and inverse-logit transformation can be used, is appropriate when N is finite or
19 approaching infinite. Simulation results suggest that the inverse-normal statistic offers
20 the best trade-off between size and power.² The null hypothesis for these tests is that
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22 ² Maddala and Wu (1999) and Maddala et al. (2000) find that the Fisher-type test is superior to the IPS
23 test, which in turn is more powerful than the LLC test. Choi (2001) shows that the empirical sizes of the
24 IPS and Fisher tests are reasonably close to their nominal sizes of 0.05 when N is small, but the IPS test
25 has the most stable size. In terms of the size-adjusted power, the Fisher-type test seems to be superior to
26 the IPS test.
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1 each series in the panel contains a unit root, and the alternative hypothesis allows for
2 some (but not all) of the individual series to have unit roots (i.e., these tests are designed
3 to reject the null hypothesis only when the evidence against it is sufficiently
4 overwhelming). Alternatively, tests by Hadri (2000) and Hadri and Larson (2005)
5 reverse the roles and considered the null hypothesis of stationarity against the
6 alternative of a unit root. However, these tests are designed for cases with large T and
7 moderately sized N. Hlouskova and Wagner (2006) performed a large-scale Monte
8 Carlo simulation to study the size and power of the panel-unit root and stationarity test,
9 finding that the panel stationarity test of Hadri (2000) and Hadri and Larsson (2005)
10 perform poorly.
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24 Recent literature has shown that structural changes which shift the mean and/or the
25 trend of the individual time series could bias the results of the unit-root test (see
26 Carrion-i-Silvestre et al., 2005, or Bai and Carrion-i-Silvestre, 2009). In our case, we
27 have restricted the sample to a period without important (known) structural breaks to
28 minimize their possible effects. Moreover, to implement this test, our sample should be
29 larger (large T and moderately sized N). Romero-Avila (2008)³ tested both per capita
30 GDP and per capita CO₂ in a larger sample and found that both variables exhibit a trend
31 of broken stationarity for European countries.
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45 As a result, we have implemented LLC, IPS and inverse-normal Fisher-type tests,
46 allowing for the incorporation of trends and showing good finite-sample properties (see
47 Table A1). When the trend is included, the null hypothesis (“all panels contain unit
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52 ³ See Romero-Avila (2008) for a detailed analysis of unit roots, including structural breaks for both per
53 capita GDP and per capita CO₂.
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1 roots”) is rejected for both per capita CO₂ and per capita GDP in all tests except the IPS
2 test for per capita GDP.
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5 [insert Table A1 here]
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11 *Testing for cross-sectional independence*
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14 Cross-sectional dependence may lead to lost efficiency in estimates. Accordingly, we
15 have performed a bias-corrected LM test based on the paper by Baltagi et al. (2012),
16 who developed a scaled version of the LM test in the context of a fixed-effects,
17 homogeneous panel-data model. Results for each specification of the model are reported
18 in Table 2. The null hypothesis of cross-sectional independence is rejected for the first
19 three specifications (i.e., before including the time effects). Once the time dummies
20 and/or the country-specific trends are included in the model, there is no evidence of
21 cross-sectional dependence in the results.
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38 *Goodness of fit and residual analysis*
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41 A detailed study of the residuals from the preferred model (Column 5 in Table 2) shows
42 a correct fit. First, the residuals do not show a deviation from normality (see the left
43 panel in Figure A1). Apart from very few possible outliers, the normal QQ-plot reveals
44 a good fit for normality. In fact, after just removing the most extreme outlier (1 residual
45 out of 387), the p-values of the Jarque-Bera and Shapiro-Wilk tests for normality are
46 0.156 and 0.179, respectively. Furthermore, there is no evidence of any clusters of
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countries in terms of fitting qualities that differ from those of the whole sample (see the right panel in Figure A1).

[insert Figure A1 here]

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Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
CO ₂ pc	387	9.32	3.94	1.66	21.66
GDP pc (using ppp)	387	19.13	7.43	4.53	36.24
Oil prices (\$/kl using ppp)	387	933.66	412.36	292.76	2465.90
Coal prices (\$/t using ppp)	387	150.92	126.96	25.31	624.41
Gas prices (\$/m ³ using ppp)	387	431.63	196.59	89.44	1147.46
Coal prices/oil prices	387	0.19	0.19	0.02	0.89
Gas prices/oil prices	387	0.54	0.33	0.11	1.65
Oil energy independence	387	9.73	18.44	0.12	98.98
Coal energy independence	387	17.92	26.75	0.00	103.12
Gas energy independence	387	7.02	9.86	0.00	42.49
Carbon free energy independence	387	17.60	12.40	0.30	47.07

Table 2: Estimation results

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
ln(GDPpc)	0.446**	0.816***	0.537***	0.625***	0.554*
ln(GDPpc) ²	-0.038	-0.115***	-0.054	-0.037	-0.034
ln(Oil prices)	-0.055**	0.055*			
ln(Coal prices)		-0.117***			
ln(Gas prices)		-0.074***			
ln(coal/oil prices)			-0.095***	-0.089***	-0.053***
ln(gas/oil prices)			-0.056***	-0.066***	-0.017
ln(Oil energy independence)	-0.065***	-0.063***	-0.055***	-0.062***	-0.060***
ln(Coal energy independence)	-0.009	-0.007	-0.003	-0.009	-0.019**
ln(Gas energy independence)	0.012***	0.011***	0.007*	0.010***	0.004
ln(Carbon free energy independence)	-0.157***	-0.135***	-0.146***	-0.136***	-0.055***
constant	2.016***	1.789***	1.240***	0.768**	1.073***
Observations	387	387	387	387	387
R2_within	0.52	0.6	0.573	0.651	0.845
Adjusted_R2	0.493	0.575	0.547	0.603	0.816
LM test of cross-section independence (p-value)	5.053 (0.000)	4.675 (0.000)	7.726 (0.000)	1.168 (0.243)	1.544 (0.123)
Country-trends Included	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
Year-dummies included	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES
Turning point		34.7			

* p<.1, ** p<.05, *** p<.01

Table 3. Comparison between the linear model and the partially linear model

	(a)		(b)	
	Linear model	Partially linear model	Linear model	Partially linear model
ln(GDPpc)	1.661***	1.636***	0.554*	1.549***
ln(GDPpc) ²	-0.122*	-0.116*	-0.034	-0.099
ln(coal/oil prices)	0.076***	0.081***	-0.053***	0.076***
ln(gas/oil prices)	-0.175***	-0.179***	-0.017	-0.180***
ln(Oil energy independence)	-0.070***	-0.073***	-0.060***	-0.072***
ln(Coal energy independence)	0.122***	0.122***	-0.019**	0.122***
ln(Gas energy independence)	-0.001	0.000	0.004	0.001
ln(Carbon free energy independence)	-0.241***	-0.250***	-0.055***	-0.249***

Note: (a) no country-specific and year-specific effects, common nonparametric time trend. (b) country-specific effects and year-specific effects, country-specific nonparametric time trends.

Table A1: Unit root tests

	<i>per capita CO₂</i>		<i>per capita GDP</i>	
	trend included		trend included	
<i>Ho: Panels contain unit roots</i>				
LLC	-1.879 (0.030)	-3.312 (0.000)	-1.370 (0.87)	-3.645 (0.000)
<i>Ho: All panels contain unit roots</i>				
IPS	-1.850 ^a	-2.745 ^b	-0.322 ^a	-1.514 ^b
Fisher (Inverse normal)	-0.294 (0.385)	-3.048 (0.001)	2.880 (0.998)	-1.824 (0.034)

Notes: p-values in parentheses; ^a Exact critical values: -2.050 (1%), -1.900 (5%), -1.820 (10%); ^b Exact critical values when trend is included: -2.680 (1%), -2.530 (5%), -2.450 (10%).

Figure 1: Observed versus fitted national CO₂ emissions per capita.

————— CO₂ pc (log) - - - - - Fitted values

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 2

Figure 2: CO₂ emissions, GDP and energy prices.

Source: own elaboration.

Note: There is not truncation in the development process, so point A takes place earlier in time than point B. Otherwise the final point will be C, following a price increase without a rise on per capita GDP.

Figure A1. Residuals graphical analysis.

Acknowledgements

[Click here to view linked References](#)

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